

1. User Stories

1.1. List of User Stories (please consider all the list)

US 01: **As** a Bank Manager I **Want** to perform automatic classification on the concession **To** know if the customer will repay a loan and decide on the concession.

US 02: **As** a Bank Manager I **Want** to renegotiate the loan **To** recover customers who were in default.

UC 03: **As** a Bank Manager I **Want** to monitor the situation of the clients **To** know when I should change the client or renegotiate a loan.

1.2. General Rules (Consider the list as complete)

RN 01: A customer shall be considered in default if the delay in payment of any of its installments exceeds 30 days.

1.3. User Stories breakdown

1.3.1. US01 – As a Bank Manager I want to perform automatic classification on the concession To know if the customer will repay a loan and decide on the concession.

ML Objectives	ML Problem and Context:	<Specify the ML problem to be addressed and its context. The ML must be targeted at the right problem.>
	Organizational Goals:	<Specify measurable benefits that the ML solution should bring to the organization or society. For example, increase revenue by X%, increase number of units sold by Y%, number of trees saved.>
	User Goals:	<Specify what users want to achieve using ML. For example, for recommendation systems, this might involve helping users find content they like.>
	Model Goals:	<Specify acceptable metrics and measures that the model should achieve (for example, for classification problems, this might involve accuracy > X%, precision > Y%, recall > Z%).>

	ML Functionality:	<Specify the ML outputs in terms of the functionality the model will provide (eg classifying customers, predicting probabilities).>
	Leading Indicators:	<Specify measures that correlate with future success from the business perspective. This can include users' affective states when using the ML-enabled system (eg, customer sentiment and engagement).>
	Customer Expectations:	<Specify customer and end-user expectations in terms of how the system should behave (for example, how often they expect predictions to be right or wrong).>
User Experience	Accountability:	<Specify who is responsible for unexpected model results or actions taken based on unexpected model results.>
	Cost:	<Specify the costs involved in running the inferences and also the user impact of a wrong model prediction.>
	Forcefulness:	<Specify how strongly the system forces the user to do what the model tells them to do (for example, automatic or assisted actions).>
	Frequency:	<Specify how often the system interacts with users. For example, interact whenever the user requests it or whenever the system thinks the user will respond.>
	Interactiveness:	<Specify what interactions users will have with the ML-enabled system (for example, to provide new data for learning or human-in-the-loop systems where models require human interaction).>
	Value:	<Specify the added value perceived by users of forecasts to your work.>
	Visualization:	<Specify how the ML results will be presented so that users can understand them (for example, specify dashboards and visualization prototypes for validation).>
	Infrastructure	Data Streaming:
Execution Engine:		<Specify how the ML-enabled system model will be executed and consumed (for example, client-side, back-end, cloud-based, end-point of a web service).>

	Incremental Learning:	<Specify the need for skills to continually learn from new data, expanding knowledge of the existing model.>
	Integration:	<Specify the integration that the template will have with the rest of the system's functionality.>
	Safety:	<Specify how the system handles risks to prevent dangerous failures. Critical systems incorporating ML must analyze the likelihood of damage occurring and its severity.>
	Security:	<Specify how the system handles security issues (eg, vulnerabilities) to protect data. ML systems often contain sensitive data that must be protected.>
	Storage:	<Specify where ML artifacts (eg models, data, scripts) will be stored.>
	Telemetry:	<Specify which ML-enabled system data needs to be collected. Telemetry involves collecting data such as clicks on specific buttons and may involve other usage and performance monitoring data.>
Model	Algorithm:	<Specify the set of algorithms that can be used/ investigated, based on the ML problem and other concerns to consider (constraints related to model explainability or performance, for example, may limit solution options).>
	Explainability:	<Specify the need to understand the reasons for model inferences. The model may need to be able to summarize the reasons for its decisions. Other related concerns, such as transparency and interpretability, may also be relevant.>
	Inference Time:	<Specify the acceptable time to run the model and return the predictions.>
	Input \ Output:	<Specify the inputs (features) and expected outputs of the model. The set of meaningful inputs can be refined/ improved during pre-processing activities such as feature selection.>
	Learning Time:	<Specify the acceptable time to train the model.>
	Maintainability:	<Specify the need to prepare the model to undergo changes with reasonable effort (eg, refactoring, documentation, automated redeployment).>
	Model Performance:	<Specify the metrics used to evaluate the model (eg, accuracy, recall, F1-score, mean squared error) and measurable performance expectations.>
	Model Size:	<Specify the size of the model in terms of storage and its complexity (for example, for decision trees there may be a need for pruning).>
	Reproducibility:	<Specify the need to replicate the process of creating the model and its experiments.>
Data	Accuracy:	<Specify the need to obtain correct data both in train and operation.>
	Baseline:	<Specify the need for a baseline dataset approved by a domain expert that reflects the problem. It is employed to monitor other data acquired later.>

Bias:	<Specify the need to obtain fair samples of data and representative distributions.>
Completeness:	<Specify the need to obtain data containing sufficient observations from all situations in which the model will operate.>
Consistency:	<Specify the need to obtain consistent data in a specific context.>
Credibility:	<Specify the need to obtain true data that is credible and understandable by users.>
Data Operations:	<Specify which operations should be applied to the data (for example, cleaning and labeling data).>
Distribution:	<Specify the expected data distributions and how the data will be split into training and test data.>
Ethics & Privacy:	<Specify the need to obtain data to avoid adverse impacts on society (for example, list possible adverse impacts to be avoided). >
Quantity:	<Specify the expected amount of data according to the type of problem and the complexity of the algorithm.>
Real usage:	<Specify the need to obtain real data that represent the real problem.>
Source:	<Specify where the data will be taken from.>
Timeliness:	<Specify the time between when data is expected and when it is readily available for use.>